

β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine (0.5 ml) was sufficient to extract 100 μg of copper(II) quantitatively. Higher concentration of the reagents had no adverse effect on the extraction but was avoided due to reagent economy. Moreover, in presence of higher concentration of the reagents the absorbances of the reagent blanks become higher. Chloroform extracts showed a steady absorbance for at least 24 h.

Copper (II) was determined in presence of other diverse ions. Deviation of not more than $\pm 3\%$ from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit. In practice, all the pyridine bases showed similar behaviour while studying interferences. Copper(II) (48 μg) could be determined without interference in presence of 50–60 fold excess of Ni^{2+} , V^{5+} , Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} . The systems tolerated 20–25-fold excess of Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , U^{6+} , La^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Be^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . High results were obtained in presence of Co^{2+} and Pd^{2+} . Hg interfered seriously. Presence of Fe^{3+} and Zr^{4+} showed low recovery of copper. Among the anions tested 10-fold excess of borate, phosphate, bromide, phthalate, iodide, acetate did not interfere. Thiocyanate, thiosulphate, EDTA, oxalate, tartrate, citrate, fluoride and ascorbate interfered.

γ -Picoline was found to be comparatively more sensitive among the pyridine bases used. With this reagent the precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of copper(II) following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations containing 48 μg of Cu^{2+} gave a value of 48.25 μg , which varies between 46.81 to 49.68 at 95% confidence limit. The standard deviation is 1.37 μg and relative mean deviation 1.8%.

References

1. P. CHATTOPADHYAY and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 91.
2. J. H. W. FORSYTHE, R. J. MAJEE and C. L. WILSON, *Talanta*, 1958, 1, 249.
3. T. MOELLER and R. E. ZOGG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 612.
4. V. YATIRAJAN and S. P. ARYA, *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 861.
5. G. H. AYRES and I. E. SCROGGIE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 26, 470.
6. G. S. DESHMUKH and S. Y. TATWADI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. B*, 1961, 20, 506.
7. P. CHATTOPADHYAY and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 621.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1962.
9. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Von Nostrand, Princeton, 1962, Vol 3.

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Platinum using Mixed-ligand Complex Formation with Pyridine, α -Picoline, β -Picoline, γ -Picoline or 2,4,6-Collidine and Iodide

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THERE are reports^{1,2} on the extraction and separation of iodide complexes of platinum metals using tributylphosphate. In our laboratory, it has been noted that iodoplatinum(IV) with pyridine or its methyl substituted derivatives, forms mixed-ligand complexes which are extractable into chloroform. These properties of the Pt-complexes suggested that further studies of the systems might lead to the development of simple spectrophotometric method for platinum. Apart from pyridine, other bases used are α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine.

Experimental

Spectral curves and analytical measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer, and a ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used for the measurement of acidities of aqueous solutions.

Chloroplatinic acid (Johnson & Matthey) (1 g) was dissolved in distilled water (100 ml) followed by standardisation as elemental platinum³. A working solution (392 μg Pt/ml) was prepared by appropriate dilution. Chloroform (E. Merck), pyridine (B.D.H.), α -picoline (Riedel), β -picoline (B.D.H.), γ -picoline (Fluka) and 2,4,6-collidine (B.D.H.) were distilled before use. Potassium iodide (B.D.H.) and all other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Different buffer solutions were prepared by standard procedures.

General procedure: An aliquot containing 100–500 μg of platinum was mixed with 0.05 M aqueous potassium iodide (2 ml) and pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/collidine (0.5 ml). Volume of the final aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with buffer solution of desired pH. The mixture was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30 s. The separated organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water droplets. Finally, the absorbance of the organic extract was measured at respective absorption maxima against chloroform, and platinum(IV) was determined from a previously prepared calibration curve. To test the effect of diverse ions, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.

TABLE 1 - DETAILS OF EXTRACTION METHODS

Parameter	Base				
	Pyridine	α -Picoline	β -Picoline	γ -Picoline	2,4,6-Collidine
pH	2-8	2-9	8-9	2-9	3-4
λ_{max} (nm)	345	370	485	365	360
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.95×10^4	1.75×10^4	1.85×10^4	3.70×10^4	1.09×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.05	0.018

Results and Discussion

The platinum complexes absorb maximum at 345–360 nm. The reagent blanks show insignificant absorbances in the aforesaid wavelength region. The systems show steady absorbances for at least 24 h. Maximum absorbances were found to be achieved when the extractions were carried out at pH 2–8, 2–9, 8–9, 2–9 and 3–4 for pyridine, α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine, respectively. Chloroform extracts obtained in the second consecutive operations in the respective pH range virtually showed no absorbance. This indicate a complete and quantitative extraction of platinum.

The optimum reagent concentrations were 2 ml of 0.05 M aqueous potassium iodide along with 0.5 ml of pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine to extract 100–500 μg of platinum. In all cases, Beer's law was found to be valid over the concentration range 5–50 ppm of Pt. The Ringbom's optimum concentration range for the measurement was found to be from 8–50 ppm of Pt^{IV}. The molar absorptivities of the complexes (on the basis of Pt content) and the respective Sandell's sensitivities were calculated as shown in Table 1.

Platinum(IV) was determined in presence of other diverse ions. In fact all the bases, i.e. pyridine, α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine showed similar behaviour towards the extraction of platinum. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of platinum(IV) differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken.

For the determination of 392 μg of Pt^{IV} (117.6 μg for collidine) a 25-fold excess of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mo^{VI}, U^{VI}, Pb^{II}, Mn^{II}, V^V, Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cr^{III}, La^{III}, Be^{II} and Al^{III} did not interfere. A 10-fold excess of Cd^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and a 5-fold excess of Rh^{III} were tolerable. A 5-fold excess of Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} could be kept in the aqueous phase with ammonium hydrogenfluoride and citrate, respectively. Hg^{II} and Pd^{II} interfered. Among the anions tested, the followings (50-fold excess) did not interfere: oxalate, borate, phosphate, tartrate, citrate, fluoride, bromide, phthalate, acetate. Lower concentration of EDTA is permissible. However, thiocyanate, thiosulphate and ascorbate interfered seriously.

2,4,6-Collidine was found to be most sensitive among the pyridine bases used. With this reagent the precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of platinum following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations containing 117.6 μg of Pt^{IV} gives a value of 115.5 μg , which varies between 114.52 to 116.44 at 95% confidence limit. The standard deviation is 0.92 μg .

References

1. G. H. FAYE and W. R. INMAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963 35, 985.
2. E. W. BERG and E. Y. LAU, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 248.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1962.

Electrochromatography of Metal Ions on Cerium(IV) Antimonate Papers. Quantitative Separation of Palladium(II) from Several Cations†

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IN continuation of our earlier studies on other antimonates¹⁻³, we have chosen cerium(IV) antimonate papers in the present work as this substance has been found to exhibit good ion-exchange properties in column operations⁴. Simple aqueous acids, mixtures of mineral acids and their ammonium salts and buffer mixtures of weak organic acids and the corresponding ammonium salts have been chosen as the background electrolyte solutions in these studies. On the basis of migration of metal ions under the combined influence of electric field and ion-exchange, a large number of separations of metal ions have been

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